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**INTEGRATING INNOVATIVE LITHIUM RESOURCES
RECOVER TECHNOLOGY: FORGING A PATH TO A NET
ZERO FUTURE**

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Context

- The EU seeks to Improve the **sustainability and circularity** of critical raw materials in the EU market to reach carbon neutrality.
- The **EU Critical Raw Materials Act** aims to increase the extraction, recycling, and recovery of critical raw materials (CRMs) to address market dynamics concerns.
- **Lithium**, a Critical Raw Material (CRM), is crucial for the EU's green transition.

Figure 1. EU Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMs) 2023 Targets

Current efforts in the Mining Industry

Current approaches for achieving a **circular economy** and **net zero** in the mining industry involve:

- Reuse of waste and valorization of tailings
- Implementation of **environmentally friendly processes**
- Development of methodologies and guidelines to **assess environmental impacts**
- Integration of green energy systems

Figure 2. The circular economy concept in the mining and metals industry (Source: ICMM)

Objective

- Addressing the need for environmentally **sustainable lithium production** through a novel recovery process to reduce market dynamic pressures.
- Exploring **handprints** and **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)** methodological challenges e.g. prospective life cycle assessment (pLCA) for **emerging lithium recovery technologies**.

Figure 3 Metallico project Innovative battery minerals processes (www.metallico-project.eu)

Innovative processes for sustainable production and recovery of (critical) battery metals, including waste valorization.

Conventional lithium production routes

Conventional routes for lithium production, such as sulfate roasting and soda leaching processes used to recover lithium from minerals, are associated with **environmental impacts**.

Conventional lithium production methods face several challenges, including

- Significant waste generation
- Difficult waste management
- Extensive water use
- Chemical pollution risks.

Figure 4. Simplified flowsheet of lithium carbonate (Li₂CO₃) conventional production route, adapted from Kelly et al, (2021)

Novel Lithium recovery process

Figure 5. Pilot plant, METALLICO-EU project (www.metallico-project.eu)

Figure 6. Simplified flowsheet of the novel process for recovering lithium carbonate (Li_2CO_3), and valorization of waste (METALLICO)

Advantages and **handprints** include applicability to a wide range of materials, no use of chemicals or minimal use, utilization of generated residues, zero waste through recycling of input materials, and water treatment capabilities.

Environment assessment to support Emerging technology under development

Prospective Life Cycle Assessment (pLCA)

Prospective LCA differs from traditional LCA, the focus is on future scenarios of technologies or products that are still under development or not yet widely available.

Environment assessment to support Emerging technology under development

Prospective Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) challenges

Data quality and uncertainty:

- pLCA faces challenges due to the technology's novelty and maturity level (e.g., TRL, MRL).
- Uncertainty analysis is crucial to assess result reliability.

Environment assessment to support Emerging technology under development

Prospective LCA of Lithium Process in the background literature

Figure 7. Left: Simplified approach for conducting pLCA of emerging technologies. Right: Reduction in environmental impact of a novel recovery technology for Lithium carbonate from a geothermal source in the LCA study developed by Huang et al., (2021) compared to the conventional production route in the Ecoinvent v3.5 database.

Key Takeaways and Future Directions

- Environment assessments are key in supporting the metals and mining industry towards net zero and circularity.
- Early-stage assessments offer valuable insights and should be tailored to technology specifics.
- pLCA can be strategically beneficial throughout development, to support decision-making.
- The novel lithium process introduced holds great potential for sustainable recovery of metals.
- Future work focuses on conducting in-depth assessments to integrate additional improvements.

References

METALLICO: *Demonstration of battery metals recovery from primary and secondary resources through a sustainable processing methodology.* GA 101091682 [https://Metallico | Homepage \(metallico-project.eu\)](https://Metallico | Homepage (metallico-project.eu))

European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Carrara, S., Bobba, S., Blagoeva, D. (2023). *Supply chain analysis and material demand forecast in strategic technologies and sectors in the EU: a foresight study*, Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/386650>

European Commission, Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, Grohol, M., Veeh, C. (2023). *Study on the critical raw materials for the EU 2023: final report*, Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2873/725585>

European Commission - Joint Research Centre - Institute for Environment and Sustainability: *International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) Handbook - General guide for Life Cycle Assessment - Detailed guidance*. First edition March 2010. EUR 24708 EN. Luxembourg. Publications Office of the European Union; 2010 <https://data.europa.eu/doi:10.2788/38479>

Huang, T. Y., Pérez-Cardona, J. R., Zhao, F., Sutherland, J. W. & Paranthaman, M. P. (2021). Life cycle assessment and techno-economic assessment of lithium recovery from geothermal brine. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering*, 9, 6551–6560. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.0c08733>

Kelly, J. C., Wang, M., Dai, Q. & Winjobi, O. (2021). Energy, greenhouse gas, and water life cycle analysis of lithium carbonate and lithium hydroxide monohydrate from brine and ore resources and their use in lithium-ion battery cathodes and lithium-ion batteries. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling*, 174, 105762. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105762>.

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